

Challenges Encountered by the Technical Vocational Program Implementers

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Abstract:- The purpose of the study was to explore the challenges encountered by the Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) program implementers. Single case study design was utilized to determine the challenges encountered, coping mechanism and insights of the implementers. The researcher chose six TVL program implementers in General Santos City Division to undergo in-depth interview using the approved questionnaire. Participants were made to sign informed consents with the assurance of anonymity and confidentiality. The data gathered were transcribed, translated and coded to produce themes. The study revealed that unreadiness is the main challenge encountered by the program implementers. This pertained to insufficient supplies, funds, and resources, and difficulties in acquiring and purchasing machineries. As to their coping mechanism, the themes generated were teamwork, and guidance. The teamwork pertained with the partnership with other stakeholders and guidance with the learners by the program implementers. Furthermore, as to the insights shared; themes generated were beneficial for learners, and fulfillment. TVL program was beneficial among learners and it was fulfilling on the part of the implementers.

Keywords:- Educational Management, K to 12 Challenges, Technical- Vocational Livelihood (TVL), TVL Program Implementers, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quality education has been a significant aspiration of Philippine Education. Quality education means enhancing educational standards geared towards the achievement of academic excellence. Educational excellence is embodied when there is a highly effective curriculum, sufficient material resources, and efficient school principals and teachers.

As the TVL program took root, the researcher experienced teaching in one of the private schools that offered the technical vocational, and livelihood tracks. It was not easy to handle because more hands-on activities required complete equipment and other resources to achieve the learning goals expected of the learners. I have tried different teaching strategies and even teaching techniques in a real-life situation so that they could internalize how the TVL program is helpful in the 21st century. The TVL program is beneficial in developing learners' skills locally and globally. However, it requires investment in the

laboratory apparatus, equipment or machinery, and learning resources.

Furthermore, many parents prioritize exam results over a school's amenities when selecting a school for their children. Good equipment and facilities are part of a school's all-encompassing strategy for enhancing the learning environment and juggling academics with other critical extracurricular activities, such as sports or scientific labs. The benefits of infrastructure investment for a school far outweigh the initial capital costs (Aldevera & Alenton, 2019).

After many years of implementing Technical-Vocational, public school field implementers of livelihood (TVL) programs share the same opinions and rallying cries. He emphasized that there are still issues with implementing technical vocational education in the Philippines. These include a dearth of instructional resources, tools, equipment, and classroom space (Ramos 2021).

Thus, with the problems presented, there is an urgency to conduct the study to explore the challenges encountered by the Tech-Voc program implementers which based on their learning experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights that can raise issues and concerns to the top management wherein the beneficiaries will be the learners, teachers and other stakeholders.

II. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Few studies have been conducted on the TVL. Thus, this study was conducted to determine the learners' learning experiences on the program, their challenges and the Tech-Voc program implementers' problems encountered, which would serve basis in effective implementation of the program especially in General Santos City.

Several studies point out that the Tech-Voc implementers always have a significant role in preparing the senior high school graduates to be globally competitive with knowledge, skills, and abilities and have quality and well-trained teachers in TVL programs. That is why conducting this study would help bring the issue to the authorities. Giving support and empowering the implementers would boost the TVL program in the country, specifically in the locale of the study (Sabado & Allan, 2019).

In General Santos City, the TVL program of the senior high school is challenging on the part of the Tech-Voc implementers' views, experiences, and challenges regarding the program. The top management conducted a series of training and seminars for all Tech-Voc implementers that aligned to the curriculum standard of the Department of Education, where they could share their expertise and develop effective teaching strategies based on 21st-century skills.

The purpose of this single case study is to explore, describe and analyze the challenges encountered by the Tech-Voc implementers, specifically on their learning experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights towards achieving excellence in their implementation of the TVL program in their respective schools.

The study is also conducted to hear, observe and write the challenges encountered narrated by the Tech-Voc program implementers about their experiences; may they be pleasant, joyful, painful, or fearful. These challenges might be coming from their training and preparations, and even their personality, including their knowledge and wisdom, which gave the most exciting and worst experiences as Tech-Voc program implementers.

These challenges included information that helped them to be effective in their work, happy and sad moments and the impressions of the parents and stakeholders regarding their administrative functions. It also includes the problems they encountered during their organizational operations and the coping mechanism they adapted to ensure the effectiveness of their duties and responsibilities.

In addition, it also included stories about the community linkages on how they build a connection to the private individuals, private companies, stakeholders, or Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and the support they received from their colleagues or the division, region, and national office. Finally, their hopes and dreams as Tech-Voc program implementers and the insights they could share with the school and the other Tech-Voc program implementers.

A. Research Questions

- What are the learning experiences of the Tech-Voc program implementers in public senior high schools in implementing the TVL program?
- How do Tech-Voc program implementers cope with the challenges in the enhanced K-12 primary education curriculum trend, specifically in implementing the TVL program?
- What insights could the Tech-Voc program implementers share with the teachers and other Tech-Voc program implementers?

B. Theoretical Lens

The study utilized different theoretical frameworks to structure the discussion on the challenges the Tech-Voc Program Implementers encountered. The undertaking of the

present study is based on the meeting of the following theoretical framework:

C. Learning by doing

This study was anchored in the theory of American philosopher John Dewey, which takes that learning by doing. It means placing a strong emphasis on student participation for Dewey. The conventional idea that learning occurs through lectures and rote memorization was overturned by this method. Dewey gained notoriety for his claim that we learn when fully immersed in the subject matter. He thought developing a practical curriculum pertinent to students' real-world situations and experiences was the best approach. Now almost a century old, Dewey's discovery is just starting to be more relevant as contemporary researchers use empirical evidence to highlight the significance of learning by doing.

This study deals with the challenges encountered by TVL program implementers. Without taking into account the budgetary restrictions the educational system is facing, one of the difficulties in implementing the Philippines' K-to-12 launch was that the Department of Education was still dealing with issues like a lack of classrooms, teachers who were trained correctly, books, and other instructional materials, as well as the chairs and desks that students and pupils needed in class (San Diego, 2015).

Learning-by-doing is often regarded as the most effective method of instruction. Students may now have meaningful learning experiences from experimental to real-world problem-solving thanks to the Internet and several innovative communication, visualization, and simulation tools. This white paper examines what genuine learning is, how technology aids it, what makes it effective, and why it is vital (Lombardi & Oblinger, 2007).

Furthermore, multiple strands of literature on professional teacher development, teaching and learning, teacher transformation, and organizational learning are brought together in this overview. It demonstrates that process-product logic has dominated the literature on professional teacher learning, despite its low explanatory power. The review shows how the parts of three subsystems (the teacher, the school, and the learning activity) interact and mix in various ways and intensities to impact teacher learning. The drawbacks of research that focus on specific aspects or subsystems are discussed (Opfer & Pedder, 2011).

On the other side, the hallmark of TVL – its focus on practical skills and work readiness makes remote learning particularly challenging. Practical skills are often acquired through learning-by-doing, which occurs in school-based workshops and laboratories, or through hands-on experience at the workplace with the guidance of the teacher/trainer of the said program, wherein the students may acquire the necessary skills aligned to the industry standard.

The two concepts will give us an overview of the possible challenges the TVL program implementers encounter by offering the course without enough resources and knowing the system. It requires equipment for hands-on activities.

D. The Theory of Difficulty

This theory is based on the theory states that there are things that we cannot understand because they are beyond our imagination. On the other hand, some things depend on the person's personality because their perspective makes something easy or difficult. Further, the way we see things makes much difference. Some regard a problem as a challenge, while others view it as an excuse to diminish their ability. How you react to situations matters the most (Sbahi, 2018).

In connection to the study, despite the challenges encountered by the TVL program implementers, they see the problems as challenges they need to overcome by utilizing some coping mechanism. Moreover, the study participants see the challenges differently; instead of giving up, they find alternative solutions to cope with the problem.

E. Significance Of The Study

The challenges encountered by Tech-Voc program implementers on how to be successful in their implementation of technical-vocational and livelihood programs. It is encouraging to see the efforts that various colleges, training programs, and neighborhood community organizations make to guarantee that our future workforce is well-educated and marketable. It is also comforting to have the Department of Education's curriculum standard as a roadmap for future planning for vocational and technical education (Khalid, Irshad & Mahmood, 2011).

This study would benefit a group of people, especially those interested in cultivating the potential of senior high school students to become productive citizens of society. Moreover, the study results would help the higher officials of the public schools, especially the DepEd Officials, because it would provide students with basic skills, produce more competent citizens, and prepare graduates for lifelong learning, globally-competitive individual, and employment. They provide sufficient time for mastery of concepts and skills, develop lifelong learning, and prepare graduates for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, work, and entrepreneurship (Cañete, 2019).

This study will also inspire the Tech-Voc program implementers to be mentors who would be aware that as time goes by, they need to update their knowledge and skills in teaching so that they would not be obsolete but remain excellent as modern teachers who know how to teach the M-kids Generation of Today. Findings would also encourage senior high school teachers to improve their teaching instruction skills and discover teaching strategies that would be appropriate to the present generation concerning 21st-century skills. They would be guided on how to be adaptable and flexible to adjust to the workplace culture to avoid more anxieties and fears of whatever would happen along the way

while equipping themselves with the necessary skills and knowledge to become effective teachers of the future (Brophy, 2010).

Moreover, the information gathered would also motivate parents to be understanding, more cooperative, and supportive of the needs of their children and school upon knowing that teachers have passed many experiences before they would become experts in their chosen career in helping children to achieve what is required of them. As a researcher, I would be more understanding and patient in listening and recording the challenges the Tech-Voc program implementers encountered. Lastly, for the other researchers, information gathered would help them think of different variables to investigate related to the challenges faced by school heads, which would inspire other Tech-Voc program implementers to take a positive way in implementing the TVL programs in their respective schools.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized qualitative research design, specifically, single-case design, to explore the challenges encountered by the TVL program implementers in the division of General Santos City.

Qualitative research starts with a problem and places the researcher in the natural setting to interpret and analyze the data. Therefore, the type of research most appropriate for this study is qualitative. It allows to immerse in the biological context, speak with individuals, and provide a detailed description of the problem (Creswell, 2013).

Single case study research is a qualitative approach in which the researcher explores a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a case) or multiple bounded systems over time. It is through detailed, in-depth data collection, which involves various sources of information and reports a case description and case themes. This qualitative research is an inquiry approach helpful in analyzing and understanding a phenomenon (Creswell, 2012; Yin, 2014).

Specifically, the research utilized a single case study, and it is a strategy that uses a variety of data sources to produce thorough explanations of complex research phenomena in real-world settings. It is the most basic type of case-oriented research. Still, researchers can also conduct a series of case studies, each building on the one before it, or analyze several examples of the same event simultaneously in comparative research (Morgan, 2013).

Furthermore, it allows much detail to be collected. Other research designs would not quickly obtain that. It tends to be conducted in rare cases where large samples of similar participants are unavailable. However, researchers focus on understanding people's subjective experiences by collecting relatively unstructured data such as detailed interviews and analyzing it using narrative rather than quantitative techniques (Morgan, Pullon, Macdonald, McKinlay & Gray, 2017).

IV. RESULT

A. Description of the Participants

Six participants were interviewed for this study. They were particularly Tech-Voc program implementers who were fifteen years and more in service of teaching and in the field of administrative function or program implementation. This chapter presents the interview results of five cases. A pseudonym guided each case to provide anonymity and privacy for the chosen cases. I opted to have a name code based on the precious stones. Precious stones are lovely and valuable pieces of mineral or rock used mainly in jewelry. They are considered precious stones because they had a big part in the students' learning process, based on their experience as Tech-Voc program implementers.

The focus of this study deals with the challenges encountered by the Tech-Voc program implementers, what are their coping mechanisms, and insights that they could share with the teachers and other Tech-Voc program implementers. They have different characteristics, appearance, abilities, skills in an administrative function, and points of view in handling challenges in life or work. The following are the profile of the participants with their code name or pseudonym:

➤ *Silver:*

Male, 50 years old, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English, Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management, rendered thirty (30) years in the service of teaching, less than a year as Tech-Voc program implementer.

➤ *Diamond:*

Male, 47 years old, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics, Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management, was twenty-seven (27) years in

the service, 2014 when he decided to become a Tech-Voc program implementer.

➤ *Ruby:*

Male, 35 years old, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics, Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management who was seven (7) years in the service, 2016 when he decided as Tech-Voc program implementer.

➤ *Sapphire:*

Female, 45 years old, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English, Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management, was fifteen (15) years in the service, 2015 when she decided as Tech-Voc program implementer.

➤ *Gold:*

Male, 41 years old, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in TLE, Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management, was twenty (20) years in the service, 2017 when he decided as Tech-Voc program implementer.

➤ *Emerald:*

Male, 44 years old, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Science, Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management, was twenty-three (23) years in the service, 2016 when he applied for Tech-Voc program implementer.

B. Analysis of Themes

This part presents the analysis of the challenges encountered regarding the participants' learning experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights as Tech-Voc Program Implementers.

Table 1 Thematic Analysis of how the participant views their challenges encountered as TVL program implementers. Challenges Encountered by the TVL Program Implementer

S no.	Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
1.	Supplies were not enough for the program to be implemented.	1. Unreadiness
2.	Types of equipment were not enough for the program to be implemented.	
3.	Funds were insufficient for the program implemented.	
4.	Resources were lacking to support the program.	
5.	Financial constraints among parents and learners	
6.	Difficulties in acquiring and purchasing machinery	

➤ *Main Theme: Challenges Encountered*

This study revealed that the central challenge encountered by the Tech-Voc program implementers was the unreadiness of different schools on the programs they offered under Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL). For instance, the implementers experienced insufficient supplies and funds, lacking resources and finances, and difficulties acquiring and purchasing program machinery.

This was evident in the verbatim account of the participants as follow:

- *Silver- the challenges I encountered were when the students are facing financial difficulties in their senior high school days, especially since most of their parents are farmers.*
- *Ruby- Having not enough supplies and equipment for the program. Funds are insufficient.*
- *Gold- I encountered challenges in hard to acquire or purchase machinery and supplies because of a lack of*

finances, wherein the school was not to support the other needs of the school.

- *Emerald- Insufficient finances are why the school cannot address the specific needs of the program and also, for the learners.*
- *Sapphire- Lack of resources.*

In his study "Becoming Successful K to 12 Implementers: Operational Preparedness of Senior High Schools in Hagonoy, Bulacan, Philippines," Perez (2018) found that the most frequent issues faced by school administrators in the implementation of the program were a lack of instructional resources and inadequate classroom space. To improve the operational readiness of the SHS program, the Department of Education (DepEd) must concentrate on giving these resources to schools.

Another study cited by Gharibi and Mushayt (2013) and Maffea (2020) found that the lack of resources was evident in high-poverty and middle-class areas. It is hard for schools to afford to purchase learning or instructional materials for the needs of the teachers, wherein the school lacks funds. That could mean they turned to textbooks, or they turned to using a projector to allow the students to see the teacher's screen.

Thus, during the implementation of the K to 12, specifically the program TVL, most of the schools were not ready to cater to the needs of the learners only if the program implementers connected with the different stakeholders, private companies, government agencies, and Non-Government Organizations for financial support and other requirements of the school.

Table 2 Thematic Analysis of how the participant cope up with their challenges encountered as TVL program implementers.
Coping Mechanism of the TVL Program Implementers

S no.	Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
1.	Tapped and looked for the stakeholders	1. Teamwork
2.	It is linked to other companies and agencies as stakeholders.	
3.	I asked for assistance from the experts to plan and organize different TVL programs' activities.	
4.	Increased community partnerships and linkages	
5.	Asked support from the top management	
6.	Attended a series of training, seminars, and orientations	
7.	Asked for support from the parents	
8.	Supported morally by the parents	
9.	Developed the skills of the students	
10.	Conducted thorough monitoring of students' skills development	
11.	Planned and organized activities for students	
12.	Prepared the students' potential so that at an early age	
13.	Prepared the students in real-life situations with skills-oriented	
14.	Prepared graduates for work and tertiary education	

➤ *Main Theme: Coping Mechanisms*

The study found out that one of the coping mechanisms of the Tech-Voc program implementer was teamwork with different school stakeholders. For instance, the program implementers would be tapped and looked for the stakeholders, asked for assistance from the expert's plan and organize various activities for the TVL program, and attend a series of training, seminar, and orientations just to cope with the challenges encountered.

This was evident in the verbatim account of the participants as follow:

- *Ruby- Tap stakeholders to cope the challenges in implementing with the program. Link to other companies, agencies, and others.*
- *Gold- I cope with the challenges by conducting monitoring and evaluation of the program to come up with solutions to address the said problems.*
- *Emerald- In coping with these challenges, I ask for assistance from the experts and tapping stakeholders through community linkages so that I could plan and organize different activities for the TVL program.*

- *Emerald. The success of the program depends on the support of the parents, stakeholders, top management and teachers.*

According to John J. Murphy, author of Pulling Together: 10 Rules for High-Performance Teamwork, teamwork is crucial to a company's success. Each person is unique in their abilities, skills, and gifts. Companies may gain a competitive edge when we share them and bring them to the table for a common goal.

According to the study by Khamis (2019); Zimmerman, Roussin, and Garmston (2020); Kumar (2021), teamwork or collaboration could increase efficiency by taking on more complex tasks, improve communication by facilitating open discussion and cooperation among team members, maximize output by leveraging each team member's strengths, provide opportunities for personal growth, and act as a support mechanism for staff to have positive relationship exists between teamwork and organizational performance. It is recommended that the school managers design task and activities based on teams for better results, enhance communication, increase the level

of trust and promote the participation of every member in the decision-making process.

Indeed, teamwork is vital because it enables the team to share ideas and responsibilities to solve the encountered problems. After all, a group that works well together can succeed and produce great results.

C. Guidance

The study also revealed that guidance was one of the coping mechanisms of the Tech-Voc program implementers. It is in the sense that despite the challenges encountered by the school, the program implementers guided the students on the process of their journey in finishing the course. For instance, they developed the students' skills, conducted thorough monitoring of skills development, planned and organized activities, prepared them for real-life situations with skills-oriented, and prepared for work and tertiary education.

This was reflected in the verbatim account of the participants as follow:

- *Sapphire - Planning and organization of activities*

- *Diamond - Conduct thorough monitoring of students' skills development*
- *Gold - It prepares the students to be able easy to find job in the future because of their acquired individual skills*
- *Ruby - Enhanced the individual skills in their field of choice. Students will undergo an NCII assessment to assess their competencies learned from the program.*
- *Silver - Prepares the students' potential so that at an early age, they can survive even if they cannot proceed to college;*
- *Diamond - To prepare graduates for work and tertiary education*

The school should guide the students because this enables each individual to understand abilities and interests, to develop them as well as possible and relate them to life goals, and finally to reach a state of complete and mature self-guidance as a desirable member of the social order.

According to the Department of Education (DepEd), vocational training prepares students for specific careers, disregarding traditional, unrelated academic subjects. In TVL, students are working hand-on, job-specific instruction. Thus, the guidance of the teachers is needed.

Table 3 Thematic Analysis of how the participant shared their insights as TVL program implementers. Insights Shared by the TVL Program Implementers

S no.	Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
1.	Students can work while studying.	Beneficial for learners
2.	Students can use acquired skills.	
3.	Students can acquire National Certificate II.	
4.	TVL is a self-pace modality	
5.	TVL is beneficial to learners	
6.	Prepared the students with skills to work abroad	
7.	There was an Immersion program and JDVP training.	
8.	When students can stand on their own feet	Fulfillment
9.	When we able to transfer our skills to learners	
10.	When we empower learners in achieving their goals	
11.	When we saw students finish their course	
12.	When the students became NCII holders.	
13.	When the school maintains the 100% rate in the NC II Assessment	
14.	When students are successful in their chosen specialization	
15.	When became the agent of change.	
16.	Teaching is the noblest profession.	
17.	Teaching is self-fulfilling.	

➤ **Main Theme: Insights Shared**

The study revealed that the Tech-Voc program is beneficial for learners. Wherein students can work while studying can use acquired skills can acquire National Certificate II, with the prepared skills to work abroad, and they can get free training and assessment through the Immersion program and Joint Delivery Voucher Program (JDVP) training.

This was evidently manifested in the verbatim account of the participants as follow:

- *Diamond - Yes/To acquire a national certificate and can work while studying college*
- *Sapphire - Immersion program and JDVP training*
- *Gold - I could consider the good side of the program to is that the learners were able to have an opportunity to work locally or abroad*
- *Emerald - My view on the Tech-Voc program implementer in this program is preparing the learners for tertiary education and work, even if they could continue their education. However, they could easily find a job because of their skills.*

- *Silver - The good side of the program is that the students acquire the learning in their SHS days. They can look for a job while wanting to continue their college education.*
- *Gold - Yes, because it prepares the graduates with skills that they can compete with other individuals in their chosen job, and also be able to work abroad through their NC II.*
- *Emerald - Yes, it is the best avenue for the learners to graduate with NC II level, and it is a big help for them to be, more productive in the community*

The foundation of vocational education training is "learning by doing." The emphasis is on practical learning rather than theoretical learning. In vocational schools, students practice practical skills they need and can use them in the workplace much more frequently. Their studies aim to equip them with the skills and information necessary to function effectively in their sector of choice. Due to their abilities throughout their studies, they can quickly find employment using these.

D. Fulfillment

The Tech-Voc program implementer found the program fulfilling on their part. It is in the sense that when they can transfer their skills to learners, students can stand on their own feet when they empower learners in achieving their goals when they see students finish their course when the students become NCII holders. They are successful in their chosen specialization.

This was evident in the verbatim account of the participants as follow:

- *Silver - Yes, this is very interesting because the students after graduating grade 12, they can stand on their own feet by having the income, even if they still pursue the college education*
- *Diamond - Yes, because we were able to transfer our skills to learners*
- *Ruby - Teaching is the noblest profession. It is more than interesting*
- *Silver - When the students become NCII holders. This are the results of their perseverance, determination, and dedication towards their dreams*
- *Diamond - See students marching on stage during commencement exercises*
- *Sapphire - When students are successful in their chosen Specialization*
- *Gold - Seeing students fulfilled their dreams and gained more achievements in life.*
- *Emerald - 100% of senior high school students marching on the stage and receiving their certificates and diplomas.*

According to Calderwood (2020), by far, one of the fulfillments of a teacher is watching his/her students grow and learn. After all, that is why most of us took this job! "Lightbulb moments," where students suddenly "get" something they have been working on for some time, make teachers feel their hard work was all worth it.

V. DISCUSSION

This part presents the discussion of significant findings, comparisons of results to other existing literature, limitations, and overall significance of the study. Moreover, this study sought to explore the challenges the Tech-Voc program implementer encountered.

A. Challenges Encountered by the Tech-Voc Program Implementers.

It was revealed that unreadiness was the main challenge encountered by the TVL program implementers. Specifically, this pertained to the supplies like equipment or machinery, funds or finances, and other resources like learning materials to help produce better education.

Supplies utilized in a school program or project are called business supplies. These are purchased and typically used up during the year. The most common business supplies are staplers, sticky notes, highlighter pens, and supplies used to run copiers, printers, and other office machines.

The participants mentioned that in the program implementation, they don't have supplies to utilize to make the learning more achievable, for instance, equipment or machinery which can be used to further the learning competencies that require that equipment. School supplies impact their learning by simply allowing students to complete their work. The suitable materials can make the difference between students understanding a concept and forgetting it after class.

- *Gold - I encountered challenges in hard to acquire or purchase machinery and supplies because of a lack of finances wherein the school was not able to support the other needs of the school.*
- *Emerald - Insufficient finances are why the school cannot address the specific needs of the program and also for the learners.*

Teixeira et al. (2017) assert that essential components of learning environments in schools and universities include the structures, classrooms, laboratories, and equipment, known as education infrastructure. Substantial evidence is that high-quality infrastructure makes all possible better education, higher student results, and a decrease in dropout rates.

The program implementers were concerned about the school's finances and the resources required in the classroom. Implementing the right to education requires finances or funding to build schools, pay teachers' salaries and training, provide teaching materials, and others. Therefore, to properly implement the right to education, states should ensure that a sufficient amount of the national budget is set aside for supporting it and that the funds are used wisely and fairly to guarantee education for all and address inequities.

However, in the Philippines, K-to-12 was implemented without considering our educational system's financial limitations. As a result, the Department of Education is still dealing with issues like a lack of classrooms, adequately trained teachers, books and other instructional materials, and the chairs and desks that students and pupils need (San Diego, 2015).

To a study by Malorca et al. (2017), the Philippines is not ready for the basic education program K-12 curriculum. The lack of funds and unavailability of learning materials is just one of the problems of the K-12 curriculum, but the problem of the K-12 curriculum is not ended from that. When Senior High School starts, the most school needed facilities, chairs, books, and equipment for the specialization, especially public schools.

Further, the TVL program implementers also faced the problem of the lack of resources, specifically the classroom learning resources and other resources that help achieve the competencies needed.

In another study by Maffea (2020) entitled "Lack of Resources in Classrooms," she found out that the lack of resources is evident in high-poverty and middle-class areas. It is hard for schools to afford new laptops for each student, so the teachers in the classrooms must devise a way to compensate for that. That could mean they turn to textbooks, if they have enough, or they turn to use a projector to allow the students to see the teacher's screen.

She added that regardless of what they must do, the lack of resources in schools is highly detrimental to the students learning and the teachers instructing a class. A majority of students learn better by being hands-on in classrooms. Students can focus more if they have a screen right before them. If the teachers use projectors and screens to show students the work, many students will be unable to see the screen or understand what is going on. It is easier to have the screen at a table a few feet away rather than across the room at the board. The students can then work at their own pace and take more time looking at the screen.

From this, we can say that education resources are no doubt necessary in developing a conducive teaching-learning environment, especially among the Tech-Voc program implementer, because its features require a lot of hands-on activities among the learners. Using these resources could give the teacher more valuable and decisive direction than any personal efforts without the materials.

A study also conducted by Tores (2015) shows that the K-12 system in the Philippines is not fully ready for the changes that will happen in the education field in our country, with more needs for improvement and enhancement. There is also a lack of materials and facilities that the government cannot provide because of insufficient funds and places for the extension the school needs to be occupied. The shortage of textbooks, teachers' classrooms, and equipment says that the level of competency for K-12 is shallow, yet they implement it.

Finally, based on the verbatim account of the participants and the related literature, we can say that the Philippines was not ready for the k-12 curriculum, especially in public school with TVL track that needs facilities and equipment for its effectiveness. That is why government must prioritize the school needs. Give more attention to the public school with a higher number of populations, help the Department of Education build new buildings for the students' facilities, give more budgets for the equipment and material needs of the school for teaching. So that, the first generation of K-12 curriculum can reveal the success and to help promote the essence of k-12 curriculum particularly the TVL.

B. Coping Mechanism of the TVL Program Implementers

The study revealed that the Tech-Voc program implementers employed coping mechanisms like teamwork and guidance. Teamwork was done by Tapping and looking for the stakeholders or linking to other companies and agencies as stakeholders, asking for assistance from the expert's plan and organizing different activities for the TVL program, and attending a series of training, seminar, and orientations, asking support from parents and others. While the program implementers did guidance as an act of assisting the learners in the sense of developing the skills their skills, conducting thorough monitoring of skills and development, planning and organizing a series of activities, and preparing students for the real-life situation with skills-oriented, preparing them also to be work and college ready and others.

One of the coping techniques used by the program implementers was teamwork. Workplace teamwork has been shown to boost productivity, enhance communication, carry out idea-generating, distribute workload, and create an environment where each person feels valued and empowered.

According to Zimmer (2019), teamwork can increase efficiency by taking on more complex tasks, improve communication by facilitating open discussion and cooperation among team members, maximize output by leveraging each team member's strengths and skills, provide opportunities for personal growth, and act as a support mechanism for staff in the area of development.

Moreover, teamwork at the workplace has also been shown to increase innovation and creativity by allowing team members to bring unique and distinct perspectives to the table. When leveraged, effective teamwork drives the group's growth and boosts performance and success by tapping into each individual's unique strengths and attributes.

The challenges the program implementers encountered show they applied teamwork by tapping some stakeholders to be part of the team to lessen or solve the schools' challenges. This kind of strategy is prominent among public school personnel. A stakeholder is anyone involved in the welfare and success of a school. It may also be collective entities with a personal, professional, civic, or financial

interest or concern in the school. Stakeholder engagement is considered vital to the success and improvement of a school.

- *Ruby - Tap stakeholders to cope with the challenges in implementing the program. Link to other companies, agencies, and others.*
- *Emerald - In coping with the challenges, I ask for assistance from the experts and tapping stakeholders through community linkages so that I could plan and organize different activities the TVL program.*

Studies confirmed that involvement and participation of stakeholders or multiple stakeholders contribute to better management of schools. Collaboration between the school and community members is encouraged to support the school's improvement. Moreover, the importance of the active participation of the students, parents, community, and administrators in the planning and execution of the different school processes is highlighted. Thus, when stakeholders are active in creating the improvement plan, there are greater possibilities for carrying out the program (Nidao & Ancho, 2020).

From the collective ideas presented, we can say that to create effective education systems and effective learning environments. All stakeholders need to unite meaningfully through collaboration and, therefore, connection. Furthermore, successful collaboration between all stakeholders means deep listening and active doing. Open, transparent dialogue makes all parties feel seen, heard, and valued. In the end, the connection and compassion formed through those healthy relationships create successful teaching and learning outcomes that will benefit the learners.

As a result, partnerships can enhance, assist, and even transform individual partners, leading to better program quality, more effective resource utilization, and better goal and curriculum alignment (Harvard Family Research Project, 2010).

Another coping mechanism utilized by the program implementers was guidance among the learners. Even though most schools that implemented TVL programs were not ready, the implementers were doing their best to at least lessen the problems by finding some stakeholders and giving guidance to students. Many students see some lacking in their environment, especially that unmotivated one will become uninterested, resulting in low motivation and interest. It is when the guidance of teachers is highly needed.

Many students still have low motivation to learn, making them lazy, careless, and even low achievement of learning (low scores) in some subject matters. In such a case, it is a critical task for the school's stakeholders to know what factors cause them to fail. Teachers should be aware of harmful resources for their students because they serve as the primary role models in the classroom. One of them is the professors' guidance of the students; even though it may appear like a straightforward word that is simple to speak

and imagine, guidance is one of the activities that can help people who lack the drive to do anything. It is logical to conclude that instructors' assistance is a potent remedy in classrooms (Hulu, 2020).

In this study, based on the verbatim account of the participants, they made some alternative ways to elicit the challenges encountered in learning. For instance, they closely monitored students' skills development, planned and organized activities for students, prepared graduates for work and tertiary education, and others. It showed that despite the problems encountered by the program implementers, they continue to provide quality education to the learners.

- *Gold - I cope with the challenges by conducting monitoring and evaluation of the program to come up with solutions in addressing the said problems.*
- *Gold - Yes, there are a lot of supports that the school from the top management and stakeholders such as technical, resources, facilities, and equipment. I attended a series of training, seminar and orientations regarding the implementation of the TVL program.*

C. Insights Shared by the TVL Program Implementers

The study found out that TVL Program was beneficial to learners and with fulfillment on the part of the implementers, as well. Students in senior high school who choose the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood course are prepared for employment after graduation. These vocational programs benefit students all over the country by preparing them for the jobs that future OFWs will hold abroad, giving them the experience and knowledge necessary to earn the National Certifications and Certificates of Competency they will need to find employment in the future, and giving them the ability to enter college with job-ready skills, particularly for courses related to their TVL track.

The Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) track, according to Ramos (2021), is made up of specializations in the areas of agriculture and fisheries, clothing, tourism, health, processed foods and beverages, social and community development service, automotive and land transport, electronics, furniture and fixture, metal and engineering, utilities, and information and communications technologies. The Technical-Vocational According to Ramos (2021), the Livelihood (TVL) track consists of specializations in the following sectors: agriculture and fishing, clothing, tourism, health, processed foods and beverages, social and community development service, automotive and land transport, construction, electronics, furniture and fixture, metal and engineering, utilities, and information and communications technologies (DepEd Order No. 21, series 2019). The Senior High School program's TVL track exposes students to developing tangible abilities, competencies, and moral principles that could lead to financial rewards (Brillantes et al., 2019). It aims to give students' academic knowledge, technical vocational training, and skills to equip them for the demands of the community and the global workplace through highly qualified competent teachers.

In a study conducted by Bauan Technical (2019), students enrolled in this program because of the following benefits: More skills, more opportunities- TVL students get a lot of abilities and skills for future opportunities. In two years of Senior High School as a TVL student, they obtained many skills that can be used for a job. Students at TVL acquired knowledge and skills to help them in the future. More knowledge and abilities lead to more chances; college-acquired talents are advantageous. While not all TVL students will attend college, some will continue their academic careers. Students from the TVL track are not only students who focus on their academics but also on skills that can be used for their future careers. The skills they have acquired as a TVL student are an advantage, especially when the job they choose in college is related to the TVL track.

In the study, the program implementers found it beneficial to the learners; for instance, students can work while studying, prepare them with skills to work abroad, use acquired skills after finishing in a short time, and develop National Certificate II and others. Despite the challenges encountered not only by the implementers but also the learners, they can still be able to learn with the help of various stakeholders.

- *Ruby. The success of the program depends on the support of the parents, stakeholders, and top management and teachers.*
- *Silver – Yes, I will. Skillful individuals may not face hardships in life because they can acquire a job in a community where their skills suit.*

Perez (2018) stressed that problems still need to be addressed in implementing technical vocational education in the Philippines. These include the lack of learning materials, facilities, equipment, and classroom space. Based on the results, these problems did not drastically affect the perceived level of operational preparedness of the SHS program by various stakeholders- teachers, parents, and students. This outcome may be linked to the interventions conducted by teachers, as prescribed in their training.

From different kinds of literature, we can say that TVL courses are intended to provide a trained workforce in the applied sciences, technology, and business, particularly at the craft (the equivalent of high schools), advanced craft, and technical levels; providing the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commercial and economic development; to give training and impart the necessary skills to individuals who shall be self-reliant economically. At all levels of the nation's educational system and for all known and existing school types, instructional facilities or teaching and learning materials are an indispensable factor in attaining the goals.

Finally, the study also revealed that TVL courses were fulfilling on the part of the program implementers, knowing that its implementation was not organized and ready. However, teachers always become part of the solution to the school's problem. It was fulfilling; for instance, they can

transfer their skills to learners, empower learners to achieve their goals, and become NCII holders when students succeed in their chosen specialization.

- *Gold - Before I chose this career, it was already a dream that I could impart knowledge and skills to all learners wherein I am the agent to change the lives of the learners. Work is exciting because you are not only educating learners, but you are also changing their perceptions in life.*

Academic life has many fulfilling components, but teaching can be most satisfying. Teaching is a noble profession; teachers are selfless and always ready to go to any extent to help their students in all aspects of learning. It gives teachers an incredible feeling of self-satisfaction when they see their students achieve in life and apply what they have from their school (Rayan, 2019).

Despite their experiences and difficulties, teachers and program implementers may still control the learning process because, possibly, one of the most useful things we as teachers can do is to care for our students as learners. Caring pedagogies don't call for us to compromise our values or ignore conventions. They require that we represent our students as fellow human beings and devote ourselves to their success (Eyler, 2018).

Teaching is one of the most satisfying careers, claim Yeap et al. (2021). Teachers appreciate what they do for a variety of reasons. However, the capacity to influence students' lives is one of the most cherished components of education. The most satisfying experiences, according to teachers, are the daily "aha" moments they get to see. Teachers can directly feel the effects of their daily efforts when they witness pupils finally grasp a concept they have been struggling with.

Finally, the study revealed that the Tech-Voc program implementer found teaching a vocational. Based on the verbatim accounts of the participants, they dedicate themselves to delivering quality education among the students by tapping the stakeholders to solicit help, considering teaching as the noblest profession.

D. Implications for Practice

Based on the challenges encountered by the six informants of this study, the researcher was able to delve the realities of the experiences of the TVL program implementers. The researcher believed that this undertaking would be a significant source of information not only for the school heads or the study participants but also for DepEd officials and the government.

The challenges encountered by the TVL program implementers were mainly on the unreadiness of the implemented program. It implied that the government was not fully ready to implement the program. With this, the DepEd officials should consider strategic planning, implementation, and evaluation whenever they implement any projects or programs to ensure the success and smooth

implementation of the program. Further, they also need to fully furnish the supplies, funds, human power, and other needed resources for the project's success.

According to Tores (2015), the K-12 system in the Philippines is not fully ready for the changes that will happen in the field of education in our country that has more needs for improvement and enhancement. There was also a lack of materials and facilities that the government couldn't provide because of insufficient funds and places for the extension that the school needed to be occupied. The shortage of textbooks, teachers' classrooms, and equipment says that the level of competency for K-12 is shallow, yet they implement it.

Moreover, in an interview with the ACT Teachers, Rep. France Castro on Inquirer.Net, said, "DepEd's incompetence immensely impacts teachers and students' performance. The poor performance of Filipino students marks the failure of DepEd's K-12 program". Moreover, among the outputs of DepEd's incompetence and haphazard implementation of so-called education reform is curriculum congestion, which compromises adequate teaching time and students' more profound understanding. It is worsening under the case of the blended learning scheme," she added.

With the challenges the TVL program implementers encountered, they employed coping mechanisms like teamwork and guidance. It implied the program implementers were affective and vision-driven, wherein they saw and embraced the reality by making some connections or partnerships to supplement the lack of supplies, funds, and other resources in the program implemented. Despite the challenges they encountered, they were not affected by them; instead, they continued to exercise their duties and responsibilities in the school by e guiding the students throughout their journey in the course.

Studies confirmed that involvement and participation of stakeholders or multiple stakeholders contribute to better management of schools. Collaboration between the school and community members is encouraged to support the school's improvement. Moreover, the importance of the active participation of the students, parents, community, and administrators in the planning and execution of the different school processes is highlighted. Thus, when stakeholders are active in creating the improvement plan, there are greater possibilities for carrying out the project (Nicdao & Ancho, 2020).

The insights the TVL program implementers shared benefited the learners and fulfilled their part. It implied that the TVL program has good benefits among the learners; however, a lack of resources and proper implementation were the obstacles to the program's success.

According to a Bauan Technical study from 2019, students chose to participate in this program due to the following advantages: Job Ready in just two years of Senior High School as a TVL student, and they acquired many skills that could be used to obtain a job; more skills, more

opportunities- TVL students gain many, skills for opportunities to come. Students at TVL acquired knowledge and skills to help them in the future. Additional knowledge and abilities lead to more opportunities; college-acquired talents are advantageous; not all TVL students will attend college, but some will continue their academic careers there.

Finally, in this study, no generalization could be drawn from the revealed experiences of the six participants for other concerned and relevant individuals based on the outcomes of this study. As a result, further research pertinent to this study should be done at other research sites and with other purposively selected participants to validate and compare the noteworthy findings. Furthermore, some future researchers may perform related studies to see if there are any significant differences in how participants overcome the encountered challenges.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The result of this study provided insights to the TVL program implementers. The study found that challenges were met mainly on the unreadiness of the implementation. Teamwork and guidance were their coping mechanism, while the program implementers found the program beneficial for the learners and fulfillment on their part.

I believe that the TVL program has a good objective. It is designed to provide learners with job-ready skills they will need in the future. However, due to unreadiness in its implementation, the program has not yet achieved its goal. Despite this, we cannot deny the efforts spent by the program implementers and teachers in the field, receiving all the challenges and making some alternative ways to eliminate some problems encountered.

I hope that the DepEd should address the issues on implementing the TVL program while it is still taking roots up today. They need an intensive evaluation to see the root cause of the issues and problems in the field, not only for teachers but also for the learners, stakeholders, and the community. In doing this, it will somehow help address the battle cry of the program implementers.

Setting initiatives up for success requires more than just effective implementation. According to research, outcomes are significantly influenced by performance quality. As a result, if a program is implemented ineptly or only passably, its objectives are unlikely to be met, and its effects will be less significant. Success is more likely when implementation is done well. Programs that are well administered have a better possibility of providing the desired results and beneficial outcomes for kids.

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